

Analysis of interionic potentials in chalcogenide crystals with sodium chloride structure[†]

Biswajit Ghatak and Jagdhar Mandal*

University Department of Physics, T. M. Bhagalpur University, Bhagalpur-812 007, Bihar, India

Manuscript received 24 September 2008, revised 3 June 2009, accepted 3 June 2009

Abstract : Values of cohesive energy, atomization energy, force constant, IR absorption frequency, Debye temperature, Grüneisen parameter, Anderson-Grüneisen parameter and Moelwyn-Hughes parameter for 45 chalcogenide crystals of NaCl-structure are reported here. These parameters have been obtained by using the Born-Mayer and Varshini-Shukla interionic short-range repulsive interactions. Calculations have also been performed for the computation of first order volume dependence of Grüneisen parameter commonly known as second Grüneisen parameter using expressions of higher order derivatives of interaction potential within the frame work of Dugdale and MacDonald theory. The high pressure behaviour of these crystals have also been studied.

Keywords : Crystalline state properties, Grüneisen parameter, second Grüneisen parameter.

Introduction

The nature of bonding in ionic crystals has been the centre of attraction for theoretical as well as experimental physicists and chemists as it plays a vital role in solid state physics. Several attempts have been made to understand the nature of interaction between the atoms of an ionic crystal and hence to decide the form of interaction potential for such a crystal. Once the reliable form of interaction potential is known, it is possible to study the crystalline state properties of chalcogenide crystal. The crystal state properties of chalcogenides have been studied by several workers. But these investigators employed the interaction models¹⁻⁴ with repulsive parts that are either inverse power functions or exponential functions or phenomenological in nature. But none of these proved capable enough of explaining all the observed macroscopic properties of diatomic crystals. The search for the interaction potential function satisfying the essential requirements of ideal potential function⁵ still continues.

In the present study we have used the Born-Mayer⁶ and Varshini-Shukla⁷ short-range repulsive potential to evaluate the crystalline state properties of chalcogenide crystals. The reason for selecting these models lies in their suitability⁸ of evaluating their state properties as

well as molecular state properties. Moreover, these potentials fulfill the fundamental physical requirements of an ideal potential.

Method of analysis :

Crystal energy : The crystal lattice energy per ion pair can be expressed as,

$$\Phi(r) = \Phi_e + \Phi_v + \Phi_{SR} \quad (1)$$

Here, Φ_e is the long-range electrostatic Coulomb energy with Madelung constant A . It is given by,

$$\Phi_e = -Az_1 z_2 e^2/r \quad (2)$$

where, $z_1 e$ and $z_2 e$ are the electrostatic charges on the ion pairs and r is the interionic separation.

The second term, Φ_v , on the R.H.S. of the eq. (1) represents the van der Waals energy expressed as,

$$\Phi_v = -C/r^6 - D/r^8 \quad (3)$$

where, C and D are van der Waals (vdw) dipole-dipole and dipole-quadrupole co-efficients and are given by,

$$C = S_{+-} c_{+-} + S_{++} C_{++} + S_{--} c_{--}$$

and

$$D = T_{+-} d_{+-} + T_{++} d_{++} + T_{--} d_{--} \quad (4)$$

Lattice sums S_{ij} and T_{ij} have been taken from Tosi⁹ and vdw co-efficients c_{ij} and d_{ij} are taken from Shankar, Singh and Agarwal¹⁰.

[†]Paper presented in the Symposium "Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray Memorial Symposium on Chemistry Today (2008)", organised by the Indian Chemical Society held at Kolkata on August 02, 2008.

The last term Φ_{SR} on the R.H.S. of the eq. (1) is expressed as,

$$\Phi_{SR} = S/r^m \exp(-\lambda r^n) \quad (5)$$

where, S and λ are potential parameters evaluated by applying the following crystal stability conditions :

$$\Phi'(r_0) = 0$$

and

$$\Phi''(r_0) = 9kr_0/\beta \quad (6)$$

where, k = crystals structure constant and β = isothermal compressibility.

In the above equations r_0 is the equilibrium interionic separation in the lattice and the primes denote derivatives with respect to r .

The application of the above conditions to the potential functions yields the expression for the potential parameters :

$$S = \frac{r^m [Az_1 z_2 e^2/r_0 + 6C/r_0^6 + 8D/r_0^8]}{\exp(-\lambda r^n) (m + n\lambda r^n)} \quad (7)$$

and

$$\lambda = \frac{X + n - 2m - 1 + [(X + n - 2m - 1)^2 - \{4m(M + 1)\} - X]^{1/2}}{r^n 2n} \quad (8)$$

where,

$$X = \frac{9kr_0^3 + 2Az_1 z_2 e^2/r_0 + 42C/r_0^6 + 72D/r_0^8}{Az_1 z_2 e^2/r_0 + 6C/r_0^6 + 8D/r_0^8} \quad (9)$$

where,

$$z_1 = z_2 = 2 \quad \text{for chalcogenide crystals}$$

and

$$m = 0, n = 1 \quad \text{for BM model}$$

$$m = 2, n = 1 \quad \text{for Varshini-Shukla}$$

The last term Φ_{SR} of eq. (1) is the short-range overlap repulsive energy dominant in diatomic crystals. The short-range repulsive potential perturbs the spherically symmetric closed shell of an ion in a lattice as the ions are brought closer so that outer electron shells began to overlap. An additional characteristic repulsive force becomes operative resulting from the overlapping of the ions. This

repulsive force opposes the Coulumbian attractive force operating between the positive and the negative ions and causes them to come to equilibrium at finite value of the interionic distance (r_0). This repulsive force in an ion becomes dominant at a very short distance, so it is known as short-range repulsive potential (SSRP). The exact form of SSRP in literature is still lacking.

Cohesive energy :

The cohesive energy W per mole is related to the interaction potential energy function $\Phi(r)$ by,

$$W = -N \Phi(r) \quad (10)$$

where, N is Avogadro's number.

Atomization energy :

The atomization energy of diatomic crystals is of much interest since it gives a better idea of the stability of the crystals than the cohesive energy. Only a few experimental and theoretical attempts have been made to estimate E_a for some of these crystals¹¹. The values of E_a for a particular ionic crystal AB may also be computed from the interaction potential energy function by the relation,

$$E_a = W - E - I \quad (11)$$

where, E is the electron affinity for forming B^{2-} ions and I is the ionisation energy to produce A^{2+} ions. In the present calculation the values of I have been taken from Massey¹² and those of E from Ladd and Lee¹³.

Force constant (f), IR absorption frequency (ν_0) and Debye temperature (θ_D) :

The force constant f is defined as,

$$f = 1/3 [\Psi''(r_0) + 2r_0^{-1} \Psi'(r_0)] \quad (12)$$

where, $\Psi(r)$ is the non-Coulumbic part of $\Phi(r)$ and r_0 is the equilibrium interionic distance in crystalline states. Its values are taken from Sinha *et al.*⁴.

The IR absorption frequency (ν_0) is given by,

$$\nu_0 = 1/2\pi(fm)^{1/2}$$

where, m is the reduced mass.

Once the value of ν_0 is obtained, the Debye temperature θ_D can be calculated from the relation,

$$\theta_D = h \nu_0/k$$

where, h is the Planck's constant and k is the Boltzmann constant.

Grüneisen parameter :

The Grüneisen parameter γ is the first significant measure of the anharmonicity in solids. It is related to $\Phi(r)$ by,

$$\gamma = -1/6 r_0 \Phi'''(r_0) / \Phi''(r_0) \quad (13)$$

where, $\Phi''(r)$ and $\Phi'''(r)$ refer to the second and third derivatives of $\Phi(r)$.

The Anderson-Grüneisen parameter and Moelwyn-Hughes parameter :

Anderson-Grüneisen parameters δ have been computed using Chang's expression¹⁵ connecting γ and δ which was derived on the basis of Dugdale and MacDonald formula¹⁶ relating γ to the change of compressibility with volume.

The values of the Moelwyn-Hughes parameter C_1 have been computed for the potential $\Phi(r)$ using the relation,

$$C_1 = 1 - (r_0^3 \beta / 27V) \Phi'''(r_0) \quad (14)$$

where, β is the compressibility of the crystals.

Second Grüneisen parameter :

The first order volume dependence of the Grüneisen parameter commonly known as the second Grüneisen parameter is fundamental to the study of many basic phenomena in solids. It is an additional measure of the anharmonicity in solids. γ and q can be used to make predictions of a variety of physical properties such as the equation of state of a material and are related to thermodynamic properties. These are also important in the study of thermo-elastic properties of shock-waves. The latter property is especially relevant to the study of the geophysics of the earth.

In general, the Grüneisen parameter is a function of both temperature and volume. The temperature of Grüneisen parameter for a large number of diatomic crystals can be fairly determined either experimentally or theoretically. However, the explicit dependence of Grüneisen parameter on volume is not known accurately. Davies and Parker⁷ were the first to define second Grüneisen parameter q as,

$$q = [\delta \ln \gamma / \delta \ln \gamma]_T \quad (15)$$

Basset *et al.*¹⁸ proposed an expression for q using thermodynamic relations.

In this communication an attempt has been made to calculate q for chalcogenide crystals using Born-Mayer and Varshini-Shukla forms of interaction models within the frame work of Dugdale and MacDonald theory (DM).

Grüneisen parameter (γ) based on DM theory valid at all pressures may be expressed as,

$$\gamma = -1 - V/2 (\partial^2 P / \partial V^2 - 10P/9V^2) / (\partial P / \partial V + 2P/3V)^{-1} \quad (16)$$

The second Grüneisen parameter (q) derived from eq. (1) is written as,

$$\begin{aligned} q = & -V/2\gamma [(\partial^2 P / \partial V^2 - 10P/9V^2) \\ & (\partial P / \partial V + 2P/3V)^{-1} + (\partial P / \partial V + 2P/3V) \\ & (\partial^3 P / \partial V^3 - 10/V^2 \partial P / \partial V + 20P/V^3) \\ & - V(\partial^2 P / \partial V^2 - 10P/9V^2) \\ & (\partial P / \partial V + 2P/3V)^{-2} (\partial^2 P / \partial V^2 \\ & + 2/3V \partial P / \partial V - 2/3P/V^2)] \quad (17) \end{aligned}$$

Hilderbrand equation of state¹⁹ can be used to express γ and q in terms of derivatives of potential energy function.

For crystals with NaCl-structure,

$$P = -\partial\Phi/\partial V = -1/6 r^2 \Phi'(r) \quad (18)$$

$$\partial P / \partial V = -1/36 r^4 (\Phi'' - 2/r \Phi'(r)) \quad (19)$$

$$\partial^2 P / \partial V^2 = -1/216 r^6 [\Phi''' - 6/r \Phi'' + 10/r^2 \Phi'] \quad (20)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \partial^3 P / \partial V^3 = & -1/1296 r^8 [\Phi'''' - 12/r \Phi''' \\ & + 52/r \Phi'' - 80/r^3 \Phi'] \quad (21) \end{aligned}$$

where, the primes ' denote the derivatives of $\Phi(r)$ with respect to interionic separation.

Equation of state of chalcogenides : The high pressure behaviour of these crystals is investigated by determining the compression values of these crystals by using Murnaghan logarithmic equation of state expressed as,

$$V/V_0 = \exp[-1/B_0' \log_e (B_0'/B_0 + 1)] \quad (22)$$

where, B_0 and B_0' are isothermal bulk modulus and its pressure derivatives, both referred to zero pressure. The high pressure behaviour of these crystals have been shown in Figs. 1 and 2.

Fig. 1. Compression curves V/V_0 pressure P (KBar) for chalcogenide crystals based on our interionic potential models.

Fig. 2. Compression curves V/V_0 pressure P (KBar) for chalcogenide crystals based on our interionic potential models.

Results and discussion

The latest information on chalcogenide crystals is far from complete but this work tries to add a little to the knowledge of these crystals by predicting several crystal-line state properties such as cohesive energy (W), atomization energy (E_a), force constant, IR absorption frequency (ν_0), Debye temperature, Anderson-Grüneisen parameter (δ), Moelwyn-Hughes parameter (C_1) and second Grüneisen parameter (q) respectively.

Born-Mayer (BM) and Varshini-Shukla (VS) forms of short-range repulsive potential have been used to compute W and E_a of chalcogenide crystals and their values are listed in Table 1. It is found that the cohesive energy

of $AO > AS > ASe > ATe$ for both the models. The earlier works by Waddington²⁰, Rossini *et al.*²¹ and Thakur²² have also obtained the values of W but their values are not satisfactory as they have not included the van der Waals terms.

The present values of E_a compare well with the experimental values. It is observed that the inclusion of van der Waals terms improves the results expectedly and given the better agreement as this match was missing in earlier calculation. Out of the two BM and VS models, the latter presents a better result.

Table 2 lists the calculated values of f , ν_0 and θ_D . No comparison can be made for the agreement between the theoretical and experimental values as the experimental values are not available in the literature. The present calculation shows that van der Waals energy is important for heavier crystals.

It is observed that the two models give almost identical results of f , ν_0 and θ_D .

The calculated values of γ , δ , C_1 and q have been listed in Table 3. There is no experimental data to draw comparison. But the present results indicate that γ depends upon the specific volume since the values tend to increase as we move from oxides to tellurides.

We have investigated the high pressure behaviour of these crystals. The equation works well up to very high pressure. The compression curves are given in Figs. 1

Table 1. Calculated properties of chalcogenide crystals
Cohesive energy (kJ mol^{-1}), atomization energy (kJ mol^{-1}) and experimental values

Crystals	W			E_a			
	BM	VS	Expt. ¹	BM	VS	Expt. ¹	Calcd. ¹
Oxides :							
MgO	3819.11	3758.13	3899.5	912.11	851.13	1000	753
CaO	3384.28	3337.19	3510.4	931.28	884.19	1058.6	907
TiO	3773.18	3671.16	3882.8	1098.18	996.16		995
MnO	3899.34	3647.62	3815.8	754.34	702.62	912.1	545
FeO	3799.76	3735.89	3924.6	759.76	695.51		560
CoO	3803.66	3735.51	3995.7	688.60	620.51		495
NiO	3881.26	3778.49	4083.6	654.26	571.49		483
SrO	3207.57	3172.41	3330.5	878.57	843.41	1000	831
ZrO	3534.19	3474.17		891.19	831.17		837
NbO	3727.50	3610.32		963.50	846.32		896

Table-1 (contd.)

CdO	3422.12	3353.66	3782.3	212.12	143.86	615.1	210
BaO	3054.43	3027.42	3288.6	870.43	843.42	979.1	976
TaO	3813.78	3497.66		577.78	461.66		464
UO	3410.21	3348.26					
Sulphides :							
MgS	3242.60	3198.66	3748.9	633.10	589.36	774.0	746
CaS	2924.58	2890.69	3196.6	769.08	735.19	920.5	802
MnS	3131.04	3074.01	3351.4	484.54	426.51	761.5	746
SrS	2864.77	2823.36	3012.5	823.2	791.86	895.4	780
ZrS	3162.35	3105.00		816.85	759.50		770
BaS	2650.11	2624.65	2841	762.11	736.65	895.4	782
LaS	2934.98	2903.56		869.98	836.56		825
CeS	2960.08	2926.86		727.08	692.86		662
PhS	2866.09	2819.01	3092	279.0	232.02	564.8	153
ThS	3038.89	2990.02					
US	3120.75	3056.36					
Selenides :							
MgSe	2983.47	2932.77	3343	301.97	251.27	627.6	334
CaSe	2768.02	2723.78	3033.4	540.52	496.28	702.9	636
MnSe	3018.67	2961.40	3305.4	299.17	241.90		297
SrSe	2663.42	2627.40	2903.7	559.92	523.90	698.7	625
SnSe	2777.64	2734.69		169.64	126.69		202
BaSe	2527.80	2494.93	2761.4	565.80	532.93	690.4	668
LaSe	2774.24	2732.28		495.82	595.28		662
CeSe	2801.82	2756.13		637.24	449.13		524
PbSe	2718.18	3650.87		162.18	115.13		224
ThSe	2854.86	2787.27					
USe	2885.10	2803.73					
Tellurides :							
CaTe	2649.55	2616.78	2840.9	506.05	473.28	664	547
SrTe	2407.62	2355.87	2790.7	388.37	336.37	621	653
SnTe	2719.41	2683.07		195.41	159.07		173
BaTe	2440.47	2414.79	2631.7	562.47	536.79	554	622
LaTe	2697.48	2664.17		644.41	611.17		610
CeTe	2719.33	2683.20		497.33	461.20		364
PbTe	2658.01	2607.38		88.01	36.38		79
BiTe	2701.54	2663.67					
UTe	2818.49	2760.09					

Table 2. Calculated properties of chalcogenide crystals
Force constant f (Nm⁻¹), IR absorption frequency ν_o (10¹² Hz) and Debye temperature θ_D (K)

Crystals	f		ν_o		θ_D	
	Present	Calcd. ²²	Present	Calcd. ²²	Present	Calcd. ²²
Oxides :						
MgO	20.89	21.5	18.16	18.4	871.84	886
CaO	15.24	16.7	14.21	14.9	682.47	716
TiO	14.57	21.8	13.56	16.7	651.30	800

Table-2 (contd.)

MnO	20.03	19.3	15.65	15.4	751.26	741
FeO	20.06	20.7	15.63	15.9	750.36	765
CoO	19.50	21.0	15.32	16.1	735.60	775
NiO	18.41	21.9	14.91	15.6	716.21	751
SrO	14.10	14.6	12.56	12.8	603.20	616
ZrO	16.12	18.1	13.41	14.2	643.79	683
NbO	11.76	21.5	11.42	15.6	548.52	746
CdO	13.51	17.5	12.07	13.8	579.89	662
BaO	13.26	11.6	11.84	12.5	568.45	599
TaO	10.30	19.5	10.30	14.7	494.68	707
UO	14.73	16.0	12.20	12.8	585.80	612
Sulphides :						
MgS	13.69	14.4	12.30	12.6	590.49	605
CaS	10.65	12.1	9.53	6.4	457.59	309
MnS	10.82	19.3	9.00	12.1	432.37	579
SrS	10.21	10.9	8.12	8.4	390.00	404
ZrS	11.48	14.1	8.56	9.5	411.07	457
BaS	8.61	9.7	7.08	7.4	340.28	355
LaS	11.74	11.5	8.27	8.2	397.11	394
CeS	11.77	11.8	12.30	8.3	590.89	398
PbS	9.43	11.2	7.18	6.8	344.63	327
ThS	11.69	12.2	7.93	8.1	380.63	390
US	10.98	13.0	7.68	8.4	368.83	402
Selenides :						
MgSe	9.73	13.2	8.90	10.4	427.47	499
CaSe	8.00	11.2	6.75	8.0	324.06	385
MnSe	9.68	13.2	6.73	7.9	322.98	378
SrSe	7.68	10.2	5.27	6.1	253.12	294
SnSe	8.45	10.9	5.17	5.1	248.07	246
BaSe	6.71	9.1	4.50	5.3	216.20	253
LaSe	8.58	11.0	5.06	5.7	243.02	274
CeSe	8.47	11.0	5.04	5.8	241.96	277
PbSe	6.11	10.5	4.00	5.3	192.24	254
ThSe	7.50	11.4	4.39	5.4	210.86	261
USe	6.61	11.9	4.11	5.5	197.24	265
Tellurides :						
CaTe	7.95	9.9	6.28	6.3	301.69	301
SrTe	4.56	9.5	3.64	5.3	174.98	253
SnTe	8.82	10.0	4.63	5.0	222.26	239
BaTe	6.71	8.2	3.92	4.4	188.21	209
LaTe	8.98	9.7	4.50	4.7	216.13	226
CeTe	8.97	9.8	4.51	4.7	216.59	227
PbTe	7.16	9.5	3.68	4.3	176.81	206
BiTe	8.91	9.5	4.10	4.3	197.05	205
UTe	8.50	10.4	3.94	4.4	189.02	210

Table 3. Calculated properties of chalcogenide crystals
 Values of Grüneisen parameter (γ : dimensionless), Anderson-Grüneisen parameter (δ : dimensionless)
 Moelwyn-Hughes parameter C_1 and second Grüneisen parameter (q : dimensionless)

Crystals	γ			δ			C_1			q	
	BM	VS	Calcd. ¹	BM	VS	Calcd. ¹	BM	VS	Calcd. ¹	BM	VS
Oxides :											
MgO	1.10	1.24	1.61	2.20	2.48	3.22	3.20	3.48	4.20	0.93	0.96
CaO	1.15	1.29	1.62	2.31	2.57	3.24	3.31	3.57	4.24	0.94	0.67
TiO	0.67	0.92	1.59	1.34	1.84	3.18	1.66	2.27	4.18	9.92	3.18
MnO	1.12	1.27	1.68	2.34	2.53	3.36	3.24	3.53	4.31	1.16	0.78
FeO	0.97	1.15	1.64	1.94	2.29	3.28	2.94	3.29	4.28	1.56	0.95
CoO	0.91	1.10	1.63	1.82	2.20	3.26	2.82	3.20	4.26	1.74	1.02
NiO	0.68	0.92	1.60	1.37	1.84	3.20	2.37	2.84	4.20	3.16	1.54
SrO	1.27	1.39	1.74	2.55	2.78	3.52	3.55	3.78	4.52	0.88	0.67
ZrO	0.96	1.14	1.55	1.93	2.29	3.10	2.93	3.29	4.10	1.58	0.96
NbO	1.00	1.12	1.61	2.00	2.24	3.22	3.29	3.49	4.22	1.31	1.24
CdO	0.84	1.04	1.58	1.67	2.07	3.16	2.67	3.07	4.16	1.97	1.00
BaO	1.39	1.50	1.78	2.79	3.00	3.56	3.79	4.00	4.56	0.87	0.88
TaO	0.95	1.11	1.69	1.90	2.22	3.38	3.21	3.40	4.38	1.11	1.05
UO	0.90	1.11	1.66	1.80	2.23	3.32	2.79	3.23	4.32	2.29	1.25
Sulphides :											
MgS	1.15	1.29	1.76	2.31	2.59	3.52	3.31	3.59	4.52	1.07	0.75
CaS	1.25	1.37	1.74	2.49	2.75	3.48	3.49	3.75	4.48	0.98	0.71
MnS	0.87	1.07	1.69	1.74	2.14	3.40	2.74	3.14	4.40	2.06	1.14
SrS	1.28	1.41	1.86	2.57	2.82	3.72	3.57	3.82	4.72	0.99	0.73
ZrS	0.88	1.09	1.78	1.75	2.18	3.56	2.75	3.18	4.56	2.26	1.34
BaS	1.37	1.48	1.99	2.74	2.97	3.98	3.74	3.97	4.98	0.83	0.71
LaS	1.34	1.48	1.79	2.69	2.95	3.58	3.69	3.95	4.58	1.06	0.78
CeS	1.30	1.44	1.77	2.60	2.88	3.54	3.60	3.88	4.54	1.13	0.81
PbS	1.03	1.23	1.62	2.07	2.46	3.24	3.07	3.46	4.24	1.81	1.06
ThS	1.09	1.28	1.73	2.117	2.57	3.46	3.17	3.57	4.46	1.75	1.07
US	0.76	1.02	1.86	1.51	2.05	3.72	2.51	3.05	4.72	3.62	1.72
Selenides :											
MgSe	1.10	1.17	1.85	1.99	2.33	3.70	2.99	3.33	4.70	1.38	0.85
CaSe	1.04	1.20	1.82	2.08	2.41	3.64	3.08	3.41	4.64	1.31	0.83
MnSe	0.84	1.06	1.85	1.68	2.11	3.70	2.68	3.11	4.70	2.32	1.34
SrSe	1.16	1.30	1.93	2.31	2.61	3.86	3.31	3.61	4.86	1.14	0.78
SnSe	1.06	1.24	1.86	2.12	2.47	3.72	3.12	3.47	4.72	1.51	0.94
BaSe	1.19	1.33	1.87	2.37	2.66	3.74	3.37	3.66	4.74	1.12	0.77
LaSe	1.08	1.26	1.85	1.17	2.52	3.76	3.17	3.52	4.74	1.49	0.94
CeSe	0.99	1.19	2.02	1.99	2.38	3.70	2.99	3.38	4.70	1.78	1.05
PbSe	0.42	0.74	1.80	0.83	1.48	4.04	1.83	2.48	5.04	8.87	2.04
ThSe	0.52	0.83	1.76	1.04	1.66	3.60	2.04	2.66	4.60	6.44	2.47
USe	0.21	0.48	1.76	0.42	0.97	3.53	1.15	1.97	4.52	1.32	1.51
Tellurides :											
CaTe	1.23	1.37	1.98	2.45	2.74	3.96	3.45	3.74	4.96	1.10	0.77
SrTe	0.77	0.99	1.84	1.55	1.99	3.68	2.55	2.99	4.68	2.27	1.17
SnTe	1.22	1.38	1.96	2.45	2.77	3.92	3.45	3.77	4.92	1.29	0.87

Table-3 (contd.)

BaTe	1.35	1.47	2.02	2.70	2.95	4.04	3.70	3.95	5.04	1.01	0.75
LaTe	1.30	1.45	2.00	2.60	2.90	3.99	3.60	3.90	4.49	1.19	0.84
CeTe	1.25	1.41	1.74	2.49	2.82	3.48	3.49	3.82	4.48	1.29	0.88
PbTe	0.89	1.13	2.01	1.79	2.27	4.02	2.79	3.27	5.02	2.57	1.35
BiTe	1.25	1.34	2.02	2.50	2.84	4.04	3.50	3.84	5.04	1.37	0.92
UTe	0.85	0.98	1.94	1.70	2.22	3.82	2.70	3.22	4.82	3.01	1.50

and 2. The experimental data for the compressions of chalcogenide crystals are not available in the literature and hence it is not possible to draw experimental curves for these crystals.

The graphical behavior of the crystalline state properties against force constant and cohesive energy (Fig. 3), reduced mass and IR frequency (Fig. 4), interatomic distance and force constant (Fig. 5) and reduced mass versus Debye temperature (Fig. 6) are also shown.

Fig. 3. A plot of force constant versus cohesive energy for alkali earth chalcogenides.

Fig. 4. A plot of reduced mass versus IR frequency of alkali earth chalcogenide crystals.

Fig. 5. A plot of interionic distance versus force constant for alkali earth chalcogenide crystals.

Fig. 6. A plot of reduced mass versus Debye temperature for alkali earth chalcogenide crystals.

Conclusion :

Born-Mayer and Varshini-Shukla forms of interaction potential have been applied to get different crystalline state properties of chalcogenide crystals. The latter model gives encouraging results and may prove useful for further computation of the properties of such crystals.

Acknowledgement

We are extremely thankful to Professor Md. M. M. Hasan for his keen interest in the completion of this work. We are highly grateful to the learned referee for providing useful suggestions.

References

1. K. P. Thakur, *Aust. J. Phys.*, 1977, **30**, 323.
2. R. Rydberg, *Z. Phys.*, 1931, **73**, 376.
3. J. Shankar and M. Kumar, *Phys. Status Solidi (b)*, 1987, **142**, 325.
4. S. Narayan and S. Ramaseshan, *J. Phys. Chem. Solids*, 1976, **37**, 395.
5. Y. P. Varshini and R. C. Shukla, *Rev. Mod. Phys.*, 1963, **35**, 130.
6. M. Born and J. E. Mayer, *Z. Phys. (A)*, 1932, **75**, 1.
7. Y. P. Varshini and R. P. C. Shukla, *J. Chem. Phys. (USA)*, 1978, **69**, 670.
8. J. Mandal and B. Ghatak, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **84**, 145.
9. M. P. Tosi, *Solid State Phys.*, 1964, **16**, 1.
10. J. Shankar, G. G. Agrawal and R. P. Singh, *J. Chem. Phys. (USA)*, 1978, **69**, 670.
11. R. T. Sanderson, "Inorganic Chemistry", Reinhold, New York, 1967.
12. A. G. Massey, "The Typical Elements", Penguin, Middlesex, 1972.
13. M. F. C. Ladd and W. H. Lee, *Prog. Solid State Chem.*, 1965, **1**, 17.
14. S. P. Sinha and K. P. Thakur, *Indian J Pure Appl. Phys.*, 1974, **12**, 387.
15. Y. A. Chang, *Phys Chem. Solidi*, 1967, **28**, 697.
16. J. C. Dugdale and D. K. C. MacDonald, *Phys Rev.*, 1953, **89**, 832.
17. R. O. Davies and S. Parkes, *Phil. Mag. (GB)*, 1959, **4**, 341.
18. W. A. Basset, T. Takahari, H. K. Mao and J. S. Weaver, *J. Appl. Phys. (USA)*, 1968, **39**, 319.
19. J. H. Hildebrand, *Z. Phys. (German)*, 1931, **44**, 4618.
20. T. C. Waddington, *Adv. Inorg. Chem. Radio Chem.*, 1959, **1**, 158.
21. F. D. Rossini, D. D. Wagman, W. H. Evans, S. Levino and Jaffe, Selected values of Chemical Thermodynamic Properties Circ Natf Bur. St. and No. 500 US. Govt. Printing Office, Washington, DC, 1952, 1.
22. K. P. Thakur, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1975d, **256**, 529.